

**A new subspecies of *Agapanthia dahli* (C. F. W. Richter, 1820) from North-East
Kazakhstan
(Coleoptera: Cerambycidae)**

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Abstract. *Agapanthia dahli calculensis* ssp. nov. is described and illustrated from near Uskaman in north-east Kazakhstan (Sibinka River). It is characterized by poorly pubescent elytra and by antennae nearly lacking setae tufts.

INTRODUCTION

Agapanthia dahli (Richter, 1820) is an extremely polymorphic species represented in north-West Palearctic Region by many distinct local forms. Up to now, only two of them have been described from West Europe: *A. dahli sicula* Ganglbauer, 1884 and *A. dahli malmerendii* Sama, 1981, though the last one is accepted now (Sama & Löbl, 2010) as *A. sicula malmerendii* Sama, 1981, which is definitely not adequate. The territory of Russia and neighbouring countries is also inhabited by several subspecies of *A. dahli*. One of them is described bellow.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The current article was based on the collection of Dr. M. L. Danilevsky (Moscow), where many series of *A. dahli* from all over its area are preserved, as well as a number of allied species. All colour photos were arranged by the author by using the fusion of about 10 layers for each final picture.

Abbreviations were used for the collections:

- MD collection of M. L. Danilevsky, Moscow (Russia);
ML collection of M. A. Lazarev, Moscow (Russia).

DESCRIPTION

Agapanthia dahli calculensis ssp. nov.

(Figs 1-3, 6-7; Photo 1)

Type locality. North-east Kazakhstan, Sibinka River, 49°40'27.56"N, 82°39'13.12"E.

Type material. Holotype (♂): "NE Kazakhstan, Sibinka riv., 470m, 49°40'27.56"N, 82°39'13.12"E, (from *Malva*) 24.v.2002, M. Danilevsky leg." - MD. Paratypes: (25 ♂♂, 21 ♀♀): from about same locality (mostly from *Malva*), 26.v.2002 and 20.vi.2002, M. Danilevsky leg. - MD, ML; (9 ♂♂, 6 ♀♀): NE Kazakhstan, Putintzevo env., 20 km N Zyrriyanovsk, Maralikha Mt., 670m, 49°50'59.01"N, 84°22'53.06"E; 10.vi.2005, 16-20.vi.2005, M. Danilevsky - MD; (2 ♂♂, 1 ♀): from about same locality, 25.vii.1999, D. Obydov - MD; (2 ♂♂, 1 ♀): NE Kazakhstan, S Uskaman city, 450 m, 49°51'45.05"N, 82°37'53.62"E, 31.v.2005, (from *Dictamnus*), M. Danilevsky - MD.

Description. Body elongate; head with yellow pubescence, with a very dense setae line between antennae; eyes slightly exposed, deeply emarginate; lower eye lobe about as long as gena; antennae thin, reaching beyond elytral apices in males by 5 apical joints, in females - by 4 apical joints, covered by white recumbent pubescence; setae tuft of the 3rd antennal joint poorly developed (Fig. 6) and often totally absent (Fig. 7); the 1st antennal joint elongate, enlarged distally, covered by semierect setae; the 3rd antennal joint is the longest, the 4th joint shorter than the 1st, but longer than the 5th; prothorax transverse, about 1.2 times shorter than basal width in males and about 1.3 times shorter in females; tapering anteriorly; slightly widened behind middle; pronotum convex, with dense central and lateral setae stripes, shining in between, with dense, rough punctation; scutellum transversely rounded, with light pubescence; elytra parallel-sided, about 2.9. times longer than wide in males and females, narrowly rounded apically, looking dark-grey because of relatively sparse yellow pubescence, with poorly pronounced setae spots and dense lateral setae line; long, erect and semierect elytral setae evenly decreased in length from base to apex; elytral punctation rather dense and big; legs with pale dense recumbent pubescence; ventral body side with dense yellowish pubescence; male pygidium truncate, female pygidium shallowly emarginate; last abdominal sternites in males and females slightly concave.

Body length in males: 11.4-15.9 mm, width: 2.8-4.3 mm; body length in females: 12.3-17.9 mm, width: 3.3-4.5 mm.

Remark. *Agapanthia dahli dahli* (Richter, 1820) is described from "Europa", which definitely means West Europe, which must be accepted as its type locality. In Russia, we could attribute the populations from its European part to the nominative subspecies

Differential diagnosis. The new subspecies is characterized first of all by poorly developed setae tufts of antennal joints, which are very long and dense in all other geographical forms (Fig. 8) and were generally accepted as the main identification character of the species; besides: grey humeral setae stripe absent; setae patches of elytral pubescence are defused, never contrast; antennal pale pubescence white, never yellow; elytral pubescence relatively sparse, yellow, never orange.

Distribution. North-east Kazakhstan

Etymology. Named according living among small stones "Calculensis".

Figs 1-5: 1-3. *Agapanthia dahli calculensis* ssp. nov.: 1- Holotype ♂; 2- Paratype ♀, NE Kazakhstan, Putintzevo env.; 3- Paratype ♀, NE Kazakhstan, S Uskaman city; 4-5. *Agapanthia dahli dahli* (4 ♂-5 ♀). Central Russia, Samara reg.

Figs 6-8. 3rd antennal joint: 6- *A. d. calculensis* ssp. nov., Holotype; 7- *A. d. calculensis* ssp. nov., Paratype, Kazakhstan, Sibinka riv.; 8- *A. d. dahli*: West Kazakhstan-Region, Furmanovo.

Photo 1. *Agapanthia dahli calculensis* ssp. nov. Kazakhstan: Putintzevo environs near Zyryanovsk, Maralikha Mt.

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